

Effect of Two Levels of AD3EC on Weight and Feed Conversion Efficiency of Local Lambs

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Abstract

This experiment was conducted in the animal field of the College of Agriculture and the Department of Animal Production at Thi Qar University, Marshlands, from 2\1\2025 to 1\4\2025, to study the effect of two levels of AD3EC on the weight and feed conversion efficiency of local lambs. The study included twelve local lambs with an average weight ranging between 13.00 and 13.55 kg. They were divided into three treatments: the control treatment was not given AD3EC, the second treatment was given 3 ml of AD3EC, and the third treatment was given 4 ml of AD3EC. The lambs were fed the same feed mixture. The results of the experiment showed a significant increase in the weights of the third treatment, which was given 4 ml of AD3EC, during weeks 6, 8, 10, and 12, with averages of (23.25, 16.80, 32.75, 35.75, and 44.50) kg. The feed conversion efficiency showed a significant decrease in the third treatment, with an average of 4.02 kg feed/kg weight gain.

Keywords: *lambs, bioeconomy, nutritional supplements.*

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Introduction

Raising lambs is an important bioeconomy in many countries. Due to adverse climatic conditions, the productivity of pastures and nutritionally valuable fodder, which sheep need to increase their weight, especially at weaning age, has been affected. Therefore, it is necessary to provide nutritional supplements such as the AD3EC vitamin complex to improve their growth and overall performance. Each vitamin in this complex has a positive effect on the overall health of lambs, which in turn increases their weight gain. Vitamin A plays an important role in increasing immunity to resist diseases and infections and maintaining the epithelial tissue lining the digestive tract, improving the absorption of nutrients Tanumihardjo, (2011). It

also increases muscle mass growth, as indicated by Song et al., (2023). When vitamin A was injected into lambs at birth, it improved skeletal muscle growth, increasing the diameter of muscle fibers. D3 is important for bone growth, as it increases calcium and phosphorus absorption and regulates the body's metabolic processes. Vitamin D3 deficiency may cause decreased appetite and growth, osteomalacia, and impaired bone tissue development Denizhan et al., (2023). Vitamin E is considered one of the important antioxidants for maintaining cell health Lewis et al., (2019). It is also important in improving the growth of lambs, as Kanyar and Karadas, (2023) indicated that taking vitamin E has helped the growth of Awassi lambs and increased their final weight. Vitamin C is also considered a strong antioxidant

that protects cells from any damage and improves digestion and absorption, as it helps in absorbing iron from the intestines, improving the appetite of lambs Rice, (2000). This experiment aimed to determine the effect of dosing two different levels of AD3EC on weight and feed conversion efficiency in local lambs

Materials and Methods

Twelve lambs were purchased from local sheep markets in Dhi Qar Governorate and raised in the animal field at the College of Agriculture and Marshlands, University of Thi Qar, for a period of three months, from 2025 to 2025. The lambs were divided into three groups, with four lambs per group. Initial weights were recorded, ranging from 13.00 to 13.55kg on average. The first group served as the control and was left untreated for comparison with the other groups. The second group received 3 ml of AD3EC diluted with distilled water, while the third group received 4 ml of AD3EC diluted with distilled water. The lambs were treated with the respective doses of AD3EC every ten days. Regarding nutrition, all groups were fed the same concentrated ration, comprising 40% crushed barley, 25% wheat bran, 12% crushed yellow corn, 7% flour, 13% soybeans, and 3% salts. This feed was provided in two meals, morning and evening, supplemented with fodder and green forage at 3% of their body weight. Weights of all lambs were recorded initially and subsequently every 14 days until the end of the study. Feed conversion efficiency was calculated daily as the amount of feed consumed divided by the weight gained (kg of feed consumed / kg of weight gain

Results and Discussion

Lamb Weight

The results showed significant differences between the average weights of the AD3EC-treated lambs compared to the control group that was not given AD3EC during the sixth, eighth, tenth, and twelfth weeks. The third treatment, 4 ml of AD3EC, followed by the second treatment, 3 ml of AD3EC, and then the control treatment. The average weight at the sixth week was 23.25, 20.62, and 16.80 kg. At the eighth week, it was 16.80, 24.00, and 18.25 kg. At the ten week, it was 35.75, 29.35, and 20.10 kg. At the twelfth week, the average weight was 44.50, 36.60, and 21.73 kg. However, during the first two and fourth weeks of the experiment, no significant differences were observed, despite the increase in weights in the third treatment, followed by the second treatment and then the control. The average weight values for the third treatment were 16.00 kg, the weight of the second treatment was 15.97 kg, and the average weight of the first treatment, the control treatment, was 14.75 kg. Also, at the fourth week, the average weights of the third treatment were 19.55 kg, the second treatment 17.45 kg, and the control treatment 15.45 kg, as shown in Table 1.

Giving lambs AD3EC improved the weight of lambs compared to the control treatment. In a study by Parraguez et al.(2020), giving vitamins E and C to ewes pregnant with twins improved their weight and health condition, and also improved the weights of their offspring after birth, as their weights increased during weaning as well. In a study by Koyuncu et al.(2007), it was shown that the effect of injecting vitamin E into ewes during pregnancy improved the weights of lambs.

Table 1. Weight Values of Lambs in the Control Group and the Two Treatment Groups with Two Levels of AD3EC Throughout the Study Period

Experimental treatment	Lamb weights						
	Week						
	Initial weight	Weight at 2 weeks	Weight at 4 weeks	Weight at 6 weeks	Weight at 8 weeks	Weight at 10 weeks	Weight at 12 weeks
Control treatment	13.55±1.34	14.75±1.24	15.45 ±1.31	16.80 ±1.25 b	18.25 ±1.54b	20.10 ±1.13c	21.73±1.52c

Second treatment	13.20±2.36	15.97 ±2.32	17.45 ±2.24	20.62 ±2.45ab	24.00 ±2.23ab	29.35 ±2.43b	36.60±2.51b
Third treatment	13.00 ±4.13	16.00 ±4.36	19.55 ±4.48	23.25 ±4.20 a	16.80± 4.17a	35.75 ±3.40a	44.50±3.29a
significant differences	Non-significant	Non-significant	Non-significant	Significant 0.05	Significant 0.05	Significant 0.05	Significant 0.05

The first treatment, the control, was not given AD3EC. The second treatment was given 3 ml of AD3EC. The third treatment was given 4 ml of AD3EC.

Feed Conversion Efficiency

The results showed that the control treatment, which was not given AD3EC, was superior with an average of (9.21) kg feed/kg weight gain compared to the experimental treatments that were given AD3EC, with averages of (6.17, 4.02) kg feed/kg weight gain, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Feed Conversion Efficiency of Lambs (kg feed/kg weight gain) in the Control Group and the Two Treatment Groups with Two Levels of AD3EC Throughout the Study Period

Treatment	Feed conversion efficiency of lambs (kg feed/kg weight gain)
Control treatment	9.21±1.25 a
Second treatment	6.17±1.03 b
Third treatment	4.02±1.34 b
Significant	Significant 0.05

The first treatment, the control, was not given AD3EC. The second treatment was given 3 ml of AD3EC. The third treatment was given 4 ml of AD3EC.

Conclusion

We conclude that AD3EC vitamins significantly increased the weights and feed conversion efficiency of lambs compared to the control group, especially for the group that received 4 ml of AD3EC compared to the group that received 3 ml of AD3EC. This indicates that increased treatment with AD3EC had a positive role in increasing the appetite of lambs and thus

increasing their weight throughout the study period.

References

Denizhan, V., Kozat, S., & Yilmaz, A. B. (2019). Investigation of serum amyloid A, haptoglobin and fibrinogen levels in sheep infected with *Fasciola hepatica*. *Journal of Livestock Science*, 10, 53–58.

<https://doi.org/10.33259/JLivestSci.2019.53-58>

Kanyar, I. M., & Karadaş, F. (2023). Effect of melatonin and vitamin E as antioxidants on body weight and carcass traits of Awassi lambs fed a high-energy and normal diet. *Iraqi Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 54(5), 1339–1350.

Koyuncu, M. E. H. M. E. T., & Yerlikaya, H. (2007). Effect of selenium–vitamin E injections of ewes on reproduction and growth of their lambs. *South African Journal of Animal Science*, 37(4), 233–236.

Lewis, E. D., Meydani, S. N., & Wu, D. (2019). Regulatory role of vitamin E in the immune system and inflammation. *IUBMB Life*, 71(4), 487–494. <https://doi.org/10.1002/iub.1985>

Parraguez, V. H., Sales, F., Peralta, O. A., Narbona, E., Lira, R., De los Reyes, M., & González-Bulnes, A. (2020). Supplementation of underfed twin-bearing ewes with herbal vitamins C and E: Impacts on birth weight, postnatal growth, and pre-weaning survival of the lambs. *Animals*, 10(4), 652. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ani10040652>

Rice, M. E. (2000). Ascorbate regulation and its neuroprotective role in the brain. *Trends in Neurosciences*, 23(5), 209–216.

[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0166-2236\(00\)01565-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0166-2236(00)01565-4)

Song, P., Chen, X., Zhao, J., Li, Q., Li, X., Wang, Y., ... Zhao, J. (2023). Vitamin A injection at birth improves muscle growth in lambs. *Animal Nutrition*, 14, 204–212. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aninu.2023.01.003>

Tanumihardjo, S. A. (2011). Vitamin A: Biomarkers of nutrition for development. *The American Journal of Clinical Nutrition*, 94(6 Suppl), 1636S–1680S.

<https://doi.org/10.3945/ajcn.110.000238>